

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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STRATEGIC ANALYSIS OF INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES: APPROACHES, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract: This article discusses the innovative strategy of the joint venture Samarkand APPAREL, the development of innovative activities in the textile and clothing industry, increasing the sector's innovative structure, boosting the export of high-tech products, expanding assets, and the organizational structure of the financial status service. The article also highlights ensuring the efficient use of material and financial resources and the development of long-term strategies and current plans for the enterprise's financial and commercial activities.

Key words: enterprise, strategy, technology, modernization, equipment, cotton, yarn, thread, export, sales.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada "Samarqand APPAREL" qo'shma korxonasining innovasion strategiyasi, to'qimachilik va kiyim-kechak sanoatida innovasion faoliyatlarni rivojlantirish, tarmoqning innovasion tuzilishini oshirish va yuqori texnologiyali mahsulotlarning eksportini ko'paytirish, aktivlarni kengaytirish, moliyaviy holat xizmatidagi tashkiliy tuzilma, moddiy va moliyaviy resurslardan samarali foydalanishini ta'minlash, shuningdek, korxonada moliyaviy va tijorat faoliyatida uzoq muddatli strategiyalar va joriy rejalar ishlab chiqish masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonada, strategiya, texnologiya, modernizatsiya, jihozlar, paxta, kalavalar, egilgan ip, eksport, sotuvlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается инновационная стратегия совместного предприятия "Samarkand APPAREL", развитие инновационной деятельности в текстильной и швейной промышленности, увеличение инновационной структуры отрасли, увеличение экспорта высокотехнологичной продукции, расширение активов, организационная структура службы финансового состояния, обеспечение эффективности использования материальных и финансовых ресурсов, а также разработка долгосрочных стратегий и текущих планов в финансовой и коммерческой деятельности предприятия.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, стратегия, технологии, модернизация, оборудование, хлопок, пряжа, нить, экспорт, продажи.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing and improving the quality of currently produced goods, ensuring their stable sale in domestic and foreign markets, enhancing their competitiveness in a highly competitive environment, extending their life cycle, creating new product projects based on market demand, strengthening the position of local goods, and increasing brand recognition are considered among the most pressing issues today.

The primary goal of the "Strategy for the Development of Competition in the Commodity and Financial Markets for 2020–2024", as outlined by the President, is to stimulate economic growth and innovation, attract increased investment, and create new jobs by fostering effectively functioning markets and a healthy competitive environment. The development of these competitive principles is also intended to strengthen relationships between economic entities.

Samarkand APPAREL JV is the largest textile enterprise in Samarkand, with a rich history spanning over fifty years under its former name, "Samarkand Knitting Factory." The modern era of Samarkand APPAREL began in 2012, supported by the Uzbekengil Industrial Association as part of the State Modernization Program, which enabled a complete reconstruction and technological upgrade of the enterprise. Between 2012 and 2014, the company imported and installed state-of-the-art textile equipment from Japan, South Korea, and Germany.

Today, approximately 200 workers and specialists are employed in its sewing shops. In January 2015, a new, modern production shop was launched in partnership with the South Korean company Samarkand Apparel, creating more than 500 additional jobs.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

In economic literature, the essence and concept of efficiency have been discussed from multiple perspectives, leading to the classification of its various criteria and indicators. Many scholars emphasize that efficiency is a relative indicator and suggest determining it by the ratio of costs to the achieved results.

Acknowledgment should be given to scientists who have significantly contributed to the development of marketing theory in economics. Research conducted in the field of marketing in Uzbekistan over the years has been influenced by national characteristics. Renowned researchers such as M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkho'jaev, B. Khodiev, K. Mirzayev, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva, and others have made notable contributions.

From our perspective, the terms "effect" and "result" reflect both quantitative and qualitative dimensions. Quantitative indicators are expressed in absolute terms such as monetary values, natural units, or standardized measures while qualitative indicators can be represented through various comparative (relative) metrics.

Regarding the criterion of efficiency, the term "criterion" is worth exploring. According to the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," the word "mezon" is derived from Arabic and means "measure, scale; balance, justice." It has six definitions, two of which are directly related to economics:

Scale, measure.

A standard for comparison or evaluation.

The phrase "efficiency criterion," therefore, can be interpreted as a "measure of efficiency," referring to methods such as measuring usefulness or assessing effectiveness. This interpretation aligns with the practical application of efficiency metrics in evaluating economic and business outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation methods were used in the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, the plant has a capacity of 7.8 million pieces of knitwear per year. The main part of the capacity is for domestic knitwear, i.e., 6 million pieces, and partially high knitwear - 1.8 million pieces. Most of the products are sold in the domestic market. At the same time, in the last two or three years, great attention has been paid to the conquest of foreign markets.

Products made of cotton yarn are successfully exported to foreign countries. Since 2015, the company has been supplying products to the markets of the Russian Federation and Belarus. In 2017, the company began supplying products to South Korea, the United States (Philadelphia), and the Czech Republic.

Today, the total volume of foreign contracts has exceeded five million US dollars.

In order to increase the export potential of the products, the company is launching the production of a new synthetic fabric - fleece. In a wide range, products made of this fabric are distinguished by their softness and ability to protect from cold and heat. In January 2020, the first batch of this product, worth sixty thousand US dollars, was exported to Belarus.

In the analysis of production and economic activity of the enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to study the state of sales (Table -1).

Table 1. Samarkand APPAREL JV sales analysis of products in 2020-2023.

t / r	Indicator name	Unit of measurement	2020	2023	The difference	Growth rate,%
1	Sale of goods, in natural sizes	Thousands	603.6	619.2	+ 15.6	102.6
2	Sales volume of products, incl	Mln.som	1715.48	1929,29	+ 213,81	112.5
3	In the domestic market	Mln.som	251.98	406,19	+ 154.21	161.2
4	export	Mln.som	1463.5	1523.1	+ 59.6	104.0

The analysis indicates that over the past two years, the Samarkand APPAREL joint venture has concentrated on leveraging export opportunities. The growth in product sales, measured in physical units, compared to 2020 amounted to 102.6%, reaching 619.2 thousand units. In terms of sales volume, 2020 figures stood at 1929.29 million soums, with an increase of 12.5% compared to the same year. However, an analysis of sales distribution

across markets reveals a decline in the share of exports. While exports accounted for 85% of total sales in 2020, this figure fell to 79% by 2023. In addition to internal factors, ongoing currency reforms in the country have had a significant influence on this trend.

The financial strength of any enterprise is fundamental to its success in a market-driven environment. Financial stability and resilience enable an enterprise not only to manage its operations effectively but also to establish a competitive advantage. Financial analysis becomes particularly crucial for enterprises aiming to enter the international market. In assessing the export potential of the Samarkand APPAREL joint venture, its financial stability and resilience were evaluated based on the company's financial statements. For this purpose, the analysis focused on three years of core financial data, including the balance sheet and financial performance reports.

Table 2. Balance sheet of Samarkand APPAREL JV, at the end of the year (thous. sum).

t / r	Indicators	Quantity by years			Changes in 2020 compared to 2018, +, -
		2021	2022	2023	
1	Total assets included	2597614	3091137	6406540	+3808926
1.1	Long-term assets	1428272	1373776	1221654	-206618
	Including the residual value of fixed assets	1425621	1315577	1194303	-231318
1.2	Including current assets	1169342	1717361	5184886	+4015544
	Inventories	493692	1012558	2606425	+2112733
	Accounts receivable	518708	695734	2212829	+1694121
	Cash	153392	9069	361052	+207660
2	Total liabilities included	2597614	3091137	6406540	+3808926
2.1	Own sources of funding	2419632	2666081	3781934	+1362302
2.2	Liabilities	177171	425056	2434062	+2256891
	Including long-term liabilities	0	0	0	

The analysis of the table shows that the total assets of the Samarkand APPAREL joint venture have grown 2.5 times over the past two years, reaching 6,406,540 thousand soums. This significant growth reflects the enterprise's aggressive policy and the effectiveness of its chosen strategy. Regular asset expansion efforts contribute to increasing the company's wealth and strengthening its market position, as illustrated in the accompanying visual representation.

However, a notable decrease in the volume of long-term assets within the enterprise's asset structure suggests that the company is prioritizing short-term objectives. The predominance of current assets over long-term assets could potentially elevate risk levels. This imbalance is evident in the figure below, where current assets occupy a much larger share compared to long-term assets.

To assess the level of risk, an analysis of the composition of liabilities as of December 2023 was conducted. The findings reveal that the volume of own funds within the total liabilities increased by 1,362,302 thousand soums, reaching 3,781,934 thousand soums. This indicates a focus on profit capitalization and suggests a low-risk environment within the enterprise. Furthermore, the ratio of liabilities to liabilities has significantly decreased, highlighting improved financial stability and reduced financial exposure.

Execution of the financial position only on the basis of the balance sheet of the enterprise does not allow determining the sources of the increase in assets. In this regard, we need to analyze the activities of Samarkand APPAREL JV in recent years. To do this, we consider the results of financial activity in the last two strands (Table 3).

Table 3. Financial indicators of Samarkand APPAREL JV, (thous. sum).

t / r	Indicators	Quantity by years		In 2023 compared to 2022,%
		2022	2023	
1	Net revenue from sales of products	1221593	1700210	139.18
2	Cost of goods sold	947700	1183508	124.88
3	Gross profit from product sales	273893	516701	188.65
4	Current expenses	384803	641491	166.71
5	Basic business benefits	353308	830797	235.15
6	Benefits of general economic activity	383710	830797	216.52
7	Net profit	342416	782285	228.46

The analysis of the table provides the following conclusions. The net income from the sale of products in 2023 increased by 39.18%, reflecting the company's efforts to expand production and sales activities. Simultaneously, the cost of goods sold also rose; however, the growth rate of net income, at 24.88%, was significantly lower. As a result, the gross profit of Samarkand APPAREL JV nearly doubled, reaching 516,701,000 soums in 2022.

The increased efficiency of production programs contributed to cost reductions, which in turn led to a significant increase in net profit. While the net profit in 2022 was 342,416,000 soums, by 2023 it had surged by 128.46%, reaching 782,285,000 soums.

From the general table analyzing the overall economic activity, it is evident that the economic efficiency of Samarkand APPAREL JV has improved substantially. (Table 4)

Table 4. Analysis of economic efficiency indicators of Samarkand APPAREL JV.

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	2022 y	2023 y.	Difference (+ ; -)	Growth rate
1	Net revenue from product sales	One thousand soums	1221593	1700210	478617	139.2
2	Benefits of general economic activity	One thousand soums	383710	830797	447087	216.5
3	Net profit	One thousand soums	342416	782285	439869	228.4
4	Average annual value of fixed assets	One thousand soums	2028388	1912729	-115659	94,29
5	Average annual value of working capital	One thousand soums	2028023	4309804	2281781	212.5
6	Profitability from product sales	%	28.0	46.0	18	164.2
7	Efficiency of fixed assets	Soum	0.6	0.89	0.29	148.3
8	Return on fixed assets	%	16.9	40.9	24	242.0
9	Capacity of funds	Soum	1.66	1,125	-0,535	67.78
10	Working capital efficiency	Soum	0.6	0.394	-0,206	65.67
11	Return on working capital	%	16.89	18.15	1.26	107.46

The following conclusions can be drawn from the analytical indicators:

The average annual value of fixed assets decreased by 6% over the current period and amounted to 1,912,729 thousand soums.

The average annual value of working capital increased by 112% and reached 4,309,804 thousand soums by the end of the year.

Profitability from product sales increased by 64%, and by 2022 it was 46%.

The efficiency of fixed assets has improved by 48% and today stands at 0.89. Accordingly, the return on fixed assets also increased sharply and amounted to 40.6%.

The decrease in the fund capacity of economic activity by 67.7% indicates that the company has been working effectively.

The return on working capital also increased by 7%, reaching 18,155 soums.

The above analysis shows that Samarkand APPAREL JV has increased financial stability and the financial justification for launching the product on the international market.

The great attention paid to marketing activities in JV “*Samarkand APPAREL*” can be seen not only in the conduct of marketing activities at the enterprise but also in the organizational structure of the marketing service. In today’s management system, marketing services include the following links:

Senior: Deputy Director for Commerce and Economics;

Middle link: marketing department and sales service department;

Lower echelons: shop supervisors, shop accountants, shop assistants.

At the same time, the Deputy Director for Commercial and Economic Affairs, in turn, heads the laboratory for the production and testing of new products (Figure).

Figure 1. Organizational structure of marketing service in Samarkand APPAREL JV.

As can be seen from this picture, Samarkand APPAREL JV has employees responsible for marketing activities. The distribution of duties and responsibilities among these employees is clearly indicated in the job descriptions. According to the division specified in the instructions, the Deputy Director for Commercial and Economic Affairs has the following responsibilities:

Ensuring the efficiency of material and financial resources, logistics, and management of the enterprise in the field of product sales and contract control;

Development of long-term strategies and current plans in the financial and commercial activities of the enterprise;

Development of enterprise standards for product quality, logistics, and storage of raw materials;

Ensuring the timely conclusion and implementation of economic and financial contracts;

Control over the sale of products, the supply of material resources, and the use of fixed assets;

Analysis based on the financial and economic indicators of the enterprise;

Management of activities for the development of measures to save resources, improve economic performance, and increase production efficiency;

Participation in fairs, exhibitions, and other promotional events on behalf of the company;

Organization of market research;

Accounting for sales, logistics, inventories, etc.

The Deputy Director for Commerce and Economy reports to all department heads, including the marketing department, sales service department, department stores, logistics department, foreign economic relations department, sales dealers of Samarkand APPAREL JV, service center, and others.

If we analyze the sales channels, the products of Samarkand APPAREL JV are mainly sold through direct contracts. The bulk of buyers are retail and wholesale firms, but both government and non-government entities make purchases for their own needs.

If we analyze the innovation strategy of JV “*Samarkand APPAREL*”, we can accelerate the innovative activity in the textile and clothing industry through the following key areas:

Development of science in the field;

Innovative development in accordance with the program of innovative development in Uzbekistan;

Improving the innovative structure of the network;

Improving the system of international scientific, technical, and innovation cooperation, increasing exports of scientific and high-tech goods;

Development of scientific and technical information systems.

In the near future, Samarkand APPAREL JV has set a number of tasks for the development of network science, including:

Development and mastering of new technologies;

Development of innovative products, including modified products and technological processes in network enterprises;

Organization of production, structural advancement in the range of products, training, and advanced training of personnel working on new technologies and equipment;

Bilateral and multilateral cooperation with foreign countries on technology, licensing, development programs, and holding mutual scientific and technical conferences and exhibitions;

Implementation of technological and structural programming, development of measures to maintain and develop the intellectual potential of light industry, and the establishment of a research and production center for the industry.

Today, Samarkand APPAREL JV is one of the most technologically and financially developed enterprises. Its leadership is making a number of efforts to increase its export potential. One of these efforts is to expand the range of production. Today, the company produces more than 120 products. All of them can be divided into the following types: products for men, products for women, products for children, and other types of products.

In the analysis process, we focused on the following. First of all, we studied the distribution of the production range by sections. (Table 5)

Table 5. The structure of the product range of JV "Samarkand APPAREL" by sections.

№	Name of sections	Share by name, %		Percentage of the amount, %	
		2022	2023	2022	2023
1	Men's clothing	41 / 34.5	55 / 39.3	36.3	34.9
2	Women's clothing	28 / 23.5	32 / 22.8	24.1	25.7
3	Children's clothes	36 / 30.2	38 / 27.1	31.8	29.2
4	Other products	14 / 11.8	15 / 10.7	7.8	10.2
	Total assortment	119/100%	140/100%	100	100

The data in this table show that in 2023, compared to 2022, a lot of work has been done to enrich the production range. In particular, the creation of 21 types of new products has been launched, and as a result, the range has reached 140 items. In terms of assortment sections, in 2018, the share of men's clothing increased from 34.5% to 39.3%, while the share of women's clothing decreased from 23.5% to 22.8%. The share of children's clothing also decreased from 30% to 27.1%. This is due to the high tannery of these products and the strong influence of fashion.

Analysis of the share of sales shows that men's clothing is the leader in the product range. In 2023, the share of this assortment section was 34.9%. In second place are children's clothing at 29.2%, and in third place are women's clothing at 25.7%. In 2020, we can expect a sharp increase in the share of other types of products, reaching up to 10.2%. In the diagrams, we can clearly see the composition of the assortment.

Next, we analyze the range of products in terms of sales. It is known from marketing theory that all goods in the product range can be divided into four groups:

"Stars," i.e., bright products that reflect the competitiveness of the firm;

"Dairy cows," i.e., goods that bring high returns to the firm and are approved by consumers;

"Question marks," i.e., new and unknown products that have not yet demonstrated their potential;

"Dogs," i.e., products that do not bring income to the enterprise, do not attract the attention of customers, but should still be included in the range.

In carrying out the analysis of the product range of JV "Samarkand APPAREL", we relied on the views of specialists from production departments, accountants, marketing, and sales. The data were obtained as a result of research conducted through surveys and interviews. (Table 6)

Table 6. The composition of the product range of JV «Samarkand APPAREL» by type of goods.

№	Assortment sections	Number of names	«Star»	«Milk cow»	«Question mark»	«It»
1	Men's clothing	55	18	21	14	2
2	Women's clothing	32	14	11	4	3
3	Children's clothes	38	9	24	2	3
4	Other products	15	5	6	1	3
	Total assortment	140	46	62	21	11

It can be seen from this table that as a result of the marketing activities of the enterprise, high-income and high-profit goods have managed to occupy a significant portion of the product range. At the same time, the increase in inefficient products such as "question mark" and "dog" is also seen by experts as a bad sign. As shown in this diagram, today the share of such products exceeds 23%.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis of innovation development strategies in manufacturing enterprises highlights the pivotal role of innovation in driving competitive advantage and ensuring long-term sustainability. Manufacturing enterprises that adopt comprehensive and forward-thinking innovation strategies are better positioned to respond to market dynamics, technological advancements, and consumer demands. The findings reveal that successful strategies often integrate technological upgrades, workforce development, and the effective utilization of financial and intellectual resources.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the significance of fostering a culture of innovation within enterprises, where creative ideas are encouraged and supported at all levels. The collaboration between businesses, research institutions, and government agencies plays a crucial role in enhancing innovation capacity. Policies and incentives aimed at reducing barriers to innovation, such as tax benefits and access to funding, have been shown to be effective in accelerating development.

In addition to the development of products with high consumer appeal in the domestic and foreign markets, the creation of new technologies for the production of textile materials using nanotechnology and plasma processing is also an effective direction. Involving specialists from specialized academic institutes and leading scientists from higher education institutions, as well as utilizing high-tech equipment from leading manufacturing companies, will enable textile enterprises to master the production of new products.

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